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EXTENDED REALITY IN STEM EDUCATION: ADVANCES AND CONSIDERATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Technology is impacting education in a number of ways. Examples include the advent of online education, maker tools such as the Arduino, and software such as intelligent tutors. Within this context, MIT Open Learning is working on understanding, supporting, and further developing the role of computer-based immersive learning technologies including augmented, mixed, and virtual reality systems (collectively called extended reality, or XR) in education. XR has often been positioned in the market as the next disruptor that will revolutionize STEM education. Such immersive learning systems have the capacity to support learners not only in knowledge, skill, and tool mastery, but also with engagement in STEM subjects (affect), seeing oneself as a STEM practitioner (identity), broadening participation through cultural customization (diversity), communicating as a STEM professional (discourse), and more. However, many crucial challenges, related to bringing XR to class are seldom considered. In a review of literature over the last 5 years, and augmented by our own studies, we find that some aspects of immersive learning systems have been evaluated usually in isolation, without comparative analyses with other teaching modalities, and without long term analysis to correct for the novice effect. We recommend advances on 5 fronts: interdisciplinary collaborations, comparative research, in-depth exploration of learning implications, development of new research methodologies, and institutional and organizational change.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Traditional educational research focused for decades on understanding and evaluating the educational content, the classroom setting, and the behaviors and interactions that might occur in class. The advent of the internet along with the rapid development of online educational technologies has been disruptive in the last three decades. New content, new pedagogies, new policies, and new degrees are now steadily developed and adopted by a great number of educational institutions around the world [1,2] As it has previously been stated in the MIT-OEPI Report [3], it is imperative that this massive development in the field of digital learning gets paired with extensive deeply integrated research across all fields that impact learning. Within this context, MIT Open Learning is working on understanding, supporting, and further developing the role of computer-based immersive learning technologies [4-6] including augmented, mixed, and virtual reality systems (collectively called extended reality, or XR) in education.

XR has often been perceived as the next disruptor that will revolutionize STEM education., as it is expected to support pedagogical innovation, enhance distant learning, as well as demoratize access to education. The rapid development of such technologies and the large number of learning related XR applications, which are rising daily in popularity, seems to support this notion. However, such immersive learning systems have the capacity to support learners not only in knowledge, skill, and tool mastery, but also with engagement in STEM subjects (affect), seeing oneself as a STEM practitioner (identity), broadening participation through cultural customization (diversity), communicating as a STEM professional (discourse), and more [6,7].

1.1 Potential Impacts of XR in Education

XR educational technologies, in particular fully immersive VR systems, have long been described as new media with the potential to support revolutionary new approaches to education if incorporated appropriately within a well orchestrated educational ecosystem. There are many definitions of “immersion,” however for the purposes here we mean: “An immersive environment is one that generates perceptual experience of the environment from a perspective within it, giving the user the sense of “presence”: that is, the sense of really being present at that perspective”[8]. The ability to immerse in a new reality is expected to allow teachers and students to break current barriers and overcome restrictions [9-13] such as:

- Time: Students can now travel in time and experience simulations or documentation of past historical places or speculative future.
- Physical inaccessibility: Students can explore the macro and micro worlds, e.g., travel to the moon or visit the interior of a molecule.
- Physical or psychological danger: Students can now safely train in simulations of hazardous situations like a fire or a flood; or safely place themselves in a

position that might bring new or even uncomfortable types of social interaction.

- Ethical problems: Students with no prior experience can now try performing a difficult surgery.
- Cost limitations: Students can now use virtual laboratories and run virtual experiments with sensitive and costly equipment they would not have been able to access otherwise.

In addition to the aforementioned cases, through XR students are expected to be able to virtually collaborate with peers physically located elsewhere, or even with non-existent virtual characters [10]. Furthermore, they are expected to engage with virtual identities they might never encounter in the physical world (avatars, characters, agents, etc.) and to have the chance to embody them in order to explore models of experiences beyond those they would encounter through their physical world current age, race, sex, or even species [4,14-17]. Research on the effects of social identities has also shown that use of XR can positively impact aspects of social educational issues, such as stereotype threats, through the appropriate employment of role-model avatars. All these affordances have also created the hypothesis that XR environments will help raising student motivation, engagement and participation [18], hopefully leading to better and deeper learning.

Having all that said, it should be clearly noted though that it is also common knowledge among the academic community [19,20] that the use of VR technologies “for creating learning environments holds a great promise but also many challenges”[20-21]. Despite the great interest and the high hopes surrounding XR system in education, it quickly became obvious that very few instances of the educational content, and experiments evaluating their impacts, have been designed with a clear pedagogical frameworks or even particular learning theories in mind. Furthermore, although XR are presented as the solution that will advance students learning, many crucial challenges, related to bringing XR to class are seldom considered. Within this context, MIT Open Learning understands and feels the responsibility to draw special attention to the fact that only a very small number of these technologies has been properly researched and evaluated yet, therefore highlighting the great need for extensive research related to the development of the field.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Data Collection and Analysis

Current paper presents a literature review on papers related to XR in education. To collect papers included in the study, the authors conducted a search on scholar.google.com looking for “Virtual Reality in Education” and “Augmented Reality in Education” and selected the conference and journal papers that were published within the last 5 years (from 2014-2019). To further demonstrate some of our own

contributions to the area, the authors additionally included publications produced by the faculty and researchers involved in the MIT Center for Advanced Virtuality. A total of 59 conference and journal papers were considered for this study. When reading the papers authors aimed to identify research studies that would mention a particular pedagogical framework or learning theory, or evidence related to retention of learning.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Pedagogical Principles

To date, the majority of XR educational technologies are applications introducing AR elements to complement and enhance traditional teaching resources. However, as VR equipment becomes more affordable and accessible (for instance, mobile VR systems that require only inexpensive plastic or even cardboard headsets and a mobile phone), new content introduced through VR worlds has been developed at an increasingly rapid pace. Most of the times content is not designed with a clear pedagogical framework in mind, but in cases where pedagogies are mentioned or can be clearly implied, the most common among them seem to be constructivism, active learning, collaborative learning, experiential learning, situated learning followed by kinesthetic learning and embodied cognition. As new technology is developed and more elaborate immersive experiences are provided for learners, a new learning phenomenon also emerges that must be theorized, which is implicit learning through embodiment. According to early studies testing this theory, different virtual body ownership “can result in implicit changes in attitudes, perception and cognition, and changes in behavior”[22]. Furthermore, as argued literature, previous research has demonstrated that the way users behave in both the physical and virtual worlds can be influenced by these virtual self representations”[4].

3.2 Relevance Across Educational Settings

Examining current literature shows that XR content has already started to be developed for a great number of subject matters and educational levels. Although computer simulations, later developed into more elaborate VR immersive worlds, have been traditionally used in medical education, military education, flight training, and training of personnel to possibly face emergency situations, ready to use content can now be found for many K-12 or higher education courses.

3.3 XR in K-12 Education

Taking a closer look at XR resources and technology for the K-12 education level, it appears that the majority of content developed constitutes AR applications that run on mobile phones or tablets, followed by 3D non-immersive games and simulations, and a small number of immersive VR educational worlds. Content most of the time was presented in the form of exploration or simulations. Meta-analysis of 69 related studies [23] including K-12 and higher education students showed that when comparing games, simulations, and virtual worlds to one another, games played

individually showed higher learning gains in comparison to the other two cases; researchers however also found an inverse relationship between number of treatments and learning gains. In alignment with that result, researchers also found that when students were repeatedly measured when using a virtual world, this seemed to deteriorate their learning outcomes gained. Furthermore, although most of the studies mentioned positive learning gains, many of them had several research limitations or did not providing adequate statistical information to support the effect sizes. In addition to the aforementioned studies, research comparing physical artifacts to an AR enhanced digital book, and to 3D virtual objects showed that elementary school children reported preferring the AR book more than the other two options. Other studies examining AR and VR in K-12 show that without proper guidance students tend to find this technology to be very overwhelming, complicated, and creating too much extra cognitive load especially to students scoring in the lower quartile on standardized exams. In addition to the lack of extended research on learning through XR at the K-12 levels, there is also a very noticeable gap in the literature in regards to the teacher experience when teaching using XR technologies. There is a similar gap regarding learning for children with special needs. At this point, it should be mentioned that the vast majority of XR resources are developed for upper elementary classes and beyond; which is in complete alignment with the fact that there is still great lack on research that can prove safety and appropriate use for children at the early education level, especially after dizziness, disorientation, and nausea have been frequently reported by many children when using VR equipment (indeed, popular VR systems typically include warnings deprecating their use with young children).

3.4 XR in Higher Education

A variety of XR resources has already started to be developed for the higher education level recently, making content for many subject matters now available. AR is usually integrated in class via “tools to track information about real-world objects of interest; hardware and software to process information; and devices to show the user the digital information integrated into the real environment”. VR seems to become mainly introduced either through educational games or simulation applications. Virtual medical labs and operation room are also increasingly deployed. Moreover, development of VR technologies “is starting to spread its influence to the AECO (Architecture, Engineering, Construction and Operations) sector through the creation of new work methodologies and techniques, as well as original interfaces for communication” [24]. In rarer cases, one can find courses introduced through venerable CAVE systems. As previously discussed, the limited research conducted in regards to the use of XR in higher education brings to light some encouraging indicators related to student motivation or peer collaboration, however most of the content and application developed so far rarely contain explicit pedagogies or mention a clear learning framework.

3.5 XR in Professional Training

Use of XR technology for professional training already has a long history, new tools though do get more and more elaborate over time as new technologies emerge. Augmented simulations have been long used in the fields of military and pilot training. Medical training has now been using plenty of XR content and platforms where doctors can either simulate difficult operations, get a view inside the patient's body, or even interact with virtual patients in order to learn how to deal with stressful situations, or just to understand how to further develop empathy with a patient. Moreover, content has now started to get developed for professionals who work in the construction field, or for personnel that has to deal with emergency situations and natural disasters. Virtual environments and online learning systems can also be used to provide workplace training on social issues such as sexual harassment and more broadly for reflective learning (in which reflection and perspective transformation are measured, not only employee completion rate). Finally, VR has started to be used in the field of traditional education for teacher training, as teachers can now interact with a virtual classroom and practice teaching under different scenarios. Having that said, it should be pointed out that there is again a lack of extended comparative studying and evaluation in regards to most of the commercial training applications that can currently be found on the market.

3.6 Research methods employed

Although various research groups have started conducting studies relevant to XR Education, up to date most of these studies are small scale research studies that only focus on understanding the use of a small educational module used within a small group of users. Such studies may provide some initial indicators in regards to whether an AR or VR module might be working for a particular group of learners, however it does not allow us to know if it works better than other more traditional approaches.

4 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

4.1 Recommendation 1: Increase Interdisciplinary Collaboration Across Fields, Using and Integrated Research Agenda

Although the need in higher education for deeper integration of research across the fields that impact learning [3] had already been highlighted and justified, we now state the need for such collaborations through the prism of the development of XR educational spaces at all educational levels. The suggested interdisciplinary scheme (Figure 1) would involve a large number of disciplines. Collaboration across these fields will continue strengthening our understanding of how learning works and will keep helping improve the design, development and evaluation of effective learning experiences. To develop and study these new educational worlds we need to combine the fields of the learning sciences, education, technology development, game design and development, arts and design, and health studies just to mention a core few. All these fields have been showing great advances when studied

individually in the past, however it is the carefully orchestrated highly interdisciplinary collaboration that now needs to come to play. We recommend that institutional and government agencies, as well as other foundations supporting learning and education research, to highly encourage development of much wider and cross-disciplinary research schemes that will allow for deeper exploration of these new fields.

Fig. 1. Fields that need to be integrated during the design of XR Education

4.2 Promote Comparative Research and Evaluation of Technologies and Pedagogies as the Critical Factor to guide Future Development and Decision Making

Having carefully examined the current landscape of XR in education, it becomes clear that development of new technologies does not always get followed by careful research-based evaluation. Even when there is a follow-up study, it almost never presents a comparative testing case including control groups. At the cognitive level, even when studies present encouraging findings regarding learning, access, and participation, there is almost never a comparative testing case that would allow us to fully understand the benefits of this new teaching method over the use of a simple 2D computer simulation or just the delivery of a traditional lecture. Given current challenges already mentioned, we recommend that a) researchers closely attempt to collaborate and coordinate their studies with XR developers, so they can carefully design long term research studies, and b) carefully plan comparative experiments between control groups using XR and more traditional teaching methods.

Furthermore, although we hypothesize some of the immediate benefits of using XR in education, such as the fact that it almost always sparks interest and enthusiasm among the students, it is still unknown to us when this novelty effect starts to wear off. It is, of course, understood that in order to study the novelty effect one should be able to use resources for an extended period of time, not easy in this case, given

that, especially regarding immersive VR educational worlds, existing resources mainly include individual or short scale modules while we still lack content that could support long term curricula.

4.3 Allow Time for In-Depth Exploration of the Field

Since XR in education is an area still in its infancy, we believe that a substantial amount of time will be required in order for researchers to properly understand and evaluate potential benefits and threats to student learning, as well as to school logistics and performance metrics. Despite the fact that XR technologies have now become more affordable, allowing for a big number of K-12 teachers, higher education instructors, and professional trainers to currently use them in class, only a very small number of short-term evaluation studies have been published up-to-date, leaving a great number of essential questions unanswered. Acknowledging all potential benefits, but also keeping in mind all potential threats, mainly cognitive, social, and physical, but also related to cybersecurity or misuse of student personal data. MIT Open Learning recommends that instructors and institutions proceed with critical awareness when incorporating XR in class, while constantly keeping themselves informed regarding updated research findings in the field.

4.4 Support the Development of new Research and Evaluations Methods

Educational studies had traditionally been using some well-established qualitative, quantitative, and mixed research methods, that would mainly employ an *external* observer/interviewer view in regards to studying human learning. During the last years MIT's agenda, through the development of the MIT Integrated Learning Initiative (MITili), is to promote a deeper integration of all learning related sciences, attempting to create a more holistic research scheme that would combine the traditional *external* view with the *internal* view usually employed by the brain and cognition and the neuroscience field. Considering how multidisciplinary *XR in education* is expected to be (Figure 1), one can expect that a great number of already existing research methods and evaluation instruments can already come to play, such as, but not limited to, a) observational protocols (mainly used at the fields of the learning sciences and cognitive psychology), b) CT or EEG scans (mainly used in the field of cognitive science), c) software usability evaluation tools (mainly used at the fields of human computer interaction and software engineering), d) cost efficiency and scalability analysis tools (mainly used in the field of finance). All the aforementioned methods and tools can already be used in order to measure different aspects of this upcoming educational world; however the need for new, advanced, more integrated assessment and evaluation instruments, that would also allow us to interconnect and correlate findings from all these different research worlds into meaningful answers, is very critical and therefore should be fully supported for the further development of the field.

4.5 Foster Cross Institutional and Organizational Communication Schemes to Facilitate Information Sharing as New Technologies and Pedagogies get Implemented and Evaluated

Although XR in education is still relatively embryonic, organizational approaches and implementation mechanisms that will eventually be employed to introduce potential XR applications can already start getting carefully designed and formed. In particular, we recommend the creation of *thinking communities* to continuously follow, internally evaluate, and disseminate information about XR educational innovations as they will get developed; and the identification and development of *change agents* and *role-model early adopters* in assisting the K-12, higher education, and professional education communities into adapting and implementing upcoming XR tools and pedagogies. Here, we refer to change agents as groups of experts, each time specialized in an appropriate educational level, collaborating toward a common end, rather than just individual visionaries [3]; and to role-model early adapters as successful groups, K-12 schools and academic institutions that are willing to pilot new, thoughtfully designed approaches [3].

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